

Cybersecurity questionnaire

Name					
Gender (Choose)	Male		Female		
Age (Choose)	19-24 years	25-30 years	31-40 years	41-55 years	
Highest Qualification (Choose)	Diploma		Undergraduate		Postgraduate
Years of experience (Choose)	1-5	6-10	11-15	Over 15	
Institution type e.g. Bank, Discount house					
Are your passwords alphanumeric?	Yes		No		
1. Physical security: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents SA-Strongly Agree, 3 represents A-Agree and 1 represents SD-Strongly Disagree					
a) Security guards, CCTV, biometrics, or related devices	SA	A	N	D	SD
b) Access to bank hardware is restricted	SA	A	N	D	SD
2. Application security: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 4 represents Agree (A), 3 represents Neutral (N), 2 represents Disagree (D) and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD)					
a) User identification and authentication are required before logging into applications	SA	A	N	D	SD
b) Application Software are always kept up-to-date	SA	A	N	D	SD
c) There is anti-malware software to detect and remove any threats from malicious software	SA	A	N	D	SD
d) Institution utilises anti-phishing solutions to prevent phishing attacks	SA	A	N	D	SD
3. Data security: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 4 represents Agree (A), 3 represents Neutral (N), 2 represents Disagree (D) and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD)					
a) Strong passwords are used to restrict access to data	SA	A	N	D	SD
b) RAID, replication, data encryption, transaction, rollback) and is able to recover from data loss or corruption within the recommended time	SA	A	N	D	SD
c) Regular backups for the data and software configuration settings are regularly performed and kept offsite	SA	A	N	D	SD
4. Network security: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 4 represents Agree (A), 3 represents Neutral (N), 2 represents Disagree (D) and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD)					
a) Firewalls with intrusion detection software and host auditing software are installed to monitor computers and servers for signs of intrusions	SA	A	N	D	SD
b) Strong passwords are used to restrict access to data	SA	A	N	D	SD
c) Virtual private networks are used as communication channels between systems.	SA	A	N	D	SD

d) Antivirus software, security-related software protect the internal the network against security breaches	SA	A	N	D	SD			
5. Internet security: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 4 represents Agree (A), 3 represents Neutral (N), 2 represents Disagree (D) and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD)								
a) Web content filtering and monitoring systems on the server and individual workstations prevent users from accessing inappropriate website or content	SA	A	N	D	SD			
b) All web-based URL always begins with HTTPS://	SA	A	N	D	SD			
c) A demilitarised zone (DMZ), firewalls' routers, and another Internet access control protects bank systems against threats from an external unsecured network	SA	A	N	D	SD			
6. Identity theft: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 4 represents Agree (A), 3 represents Neutral (N), 2 represents Disagree (D) and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD)								
a) Banks cards have been used without permission of the owner	SA	A	N	D	SD			
b) Money has been deducted from personal accounts without permission	SA	A	N	D	SD			
c) Stolen identity had been used to conduct purchases	SA	A	N	D	SD			
7. Select the security framework (s) are you using								
ITIL	Yes	No	COBIT	Yes	No	NIST	Yes	No
ISO/IEC27000	Yes	No	Others	Yes	No	None	Yes	N/A
8. Select major constraints affecting cybersecurity management at your institution: Please respond by ranking the questions below; where 5 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 4 represents Agree (A), 3 represents Neutral (N), 2 represents Disagree (D) and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD)								
Lack of skills	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Lack of policies	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Sophistication of threats	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Emerging technologies	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Lack of adequate budget	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Lack of executive support	SA	A	N	D	SD			
Do you have the office of the Chief Security Officer	Yes			No				